

EXPLORING THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF THE NANO BUSINESSES IN NAGCARLAN, LAGUNA FOR INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

Majority of existing businesses in the Philippines are nano businesses, though such term is not yet formally used in the country. Most of them are owned by marginalized business people who do not experience the benefit of the country's economic growth despite being entrepreneurs. Hence, to be able to understand the condition of the nano business industry, a hermeneutic phenomenological study was conducted in Nagcarlan, Laguna. Following the interpretivism approach as research paradigm, the lived experiences of six nano business owners in Nagcarlan were gathered through one-on-one personal interviews while the data analysis was done using the four-step process of hermeneutic phenomenological analysis. As a result, it has been concluded that despite the stagnant growth condition and income instability, the nano businesses have growth potential on the basis of their capabilities to adapt with their environment and innate business skills and abilities which only needed to be enhanced. Since it is believed that the way for the nano business to experience inclusive growth is through the involvement of the government, a proposed municipal ordinance was formulated to address concerns on documentary business requirements, capitalization aids, and trainings. To extend its outreach, a new national policy or revision of an existing law to include the nano businesses in the provisions were also recommended. All these government interventions should aim to augment the income of the nano businesses that can provide more than the necessities of their families—which is the ideal of inclusive economic growth.

Keywords: *nano business, inclusive economic growth, lived experiences, solopreneurs, business activities in Nagcarlan Laguna*

INTRODUCTION

Nature and Scope of the Problem Investigated

The term “nano business” is a newly emerging concept which is not yet formally used despite many business activities that pertains to be nano businesses are already in operation for years. In the Philippines, it was illustrated by President Ferdinand R. Marcos, Jr. as those “solopreneurs operating out of their homes or on foot, offering services such as home repair or working as *manicuristas*, or itinerant services like repairing shoes or selling snacks” (Concepcion, 2023). These types of business activities belong to the informal sector because they are not registered in any national government agency. Based on Republic Act 8425 or the Social Reform and Poverty Alleviation Act, workers in the informal sector are those poor individuals who are either self-employed or working without pay on their small-scale family-owned businesses. Meanwhile, the country had experienced a 6.4 percent growth in its gross domestic product in the first quarter of 2023 (PSA, 2023). Economic growth is said to be beneficial because it has the capability to improve the quality of life (WallStreetMojo, 2023). However, from the survey conducted by the Social Weather Stations (SWS), fifty-one percent of Filipinos, which is equivalent to 12.9 million Filipinos, felt that they are still below the poverty line as of March 2023 (CNN Philippines, 2023). This implies that many of the Filipinos rarely feel the advancement in the country’s economy.

Therefore, if there is a continuous growth in the economy while the number of economically challenged individuals is still increasing, it can be perceived that there might be inequalities in the distribution of opportunities for all to have a comfortable living condition. The promised benefits of the economic growth are not being experienced by everyone. Hence, the economic growth has to be inclusive, which means that the improved quality of life, more income-generating activities, quality job opportunities, and the like shall flow among all stakeholders of such economic growth. According to President Ferdinand R. Marcos, the nano-enterprises represent the ninety-six percent of the businesses in the Philippines (Carlos, 2023). This large percentage are the people that he mentioned in the ASEAN Summit 2023 that have the potential to contribute in the economic growth of the region and in narrowing down the development gap of the country; therefore, they need to be supported. However, there is no formal study yet focused on the nano businesses and their activities. Most studies are about the micro enterprises and informal sectors, but no specific research dedicated to the nano businesses.

Summary of Pertinent Literatures

Businesses in the Philippines are categorized based on the two criteria, namely, employment size as per Philippine Statistics Authority and asset size based on Republic Act No. 9501, also known as the Magna Carta for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises. Referring to both criteria, the micro business is still considered as the smallest unit of business in the country. Thus, the term nano business is not yet formally used to define

various business activities in the country. Likewise, in other countries, the definition of nano business is still vague and subjective. In Nigeria, Olubiya (2021) described it as a business that usually have one to three people and with capital outlay of less than Fifty Thousand Naira (approximately equivalent to 108 US Dollars). While Salami (2017) wrote that a nano business is a one-man business that mostly operated online without physical operational location where he claimed that freelancers and bloggers belong to this type of business activity. On the contrary, one claims nano business as a business that uses less than one-person workforce only, which is synonymous to a part-time business (Perazza, 2018). These differences indicate the existence of various business activities that do not fall under any of the formal business classifications in their own countries and confirmed that concrete definition to describe the nano business is still unavailable.

For this study, the Theory on Entrepreneurship of Thomas Cochran was used as reference to better understand the existence and performance of the nano business as entrepreneurs on the basis of business survival. Cochran believed that there are three influential factors affecting entrepreneurship, namely, cultural values or personality traits, social expectations, and role expectations (Chetty, 2020). This theory sees entrepreneurs as modal representations of the society where they belong, which means that there are frequently occurring traits among these entrepreneurs, however these traits are not necessarily common to all members of the group. This follows the standpoint of some sociological researches claiming that “different types of entrepreneurs may react differently to varying situations” (Bhasin, 2023) which could possibly affect their entrepreneurship development.

And so, how can the nano businesses be supported? It was already mentioned in the earlier discussion that the nano business is part of the informal sector wherein increasing poverty is an ongoing issue despite the robust growth of the Philippine economy in 2023. As a matter of fact, the Department for International Development (DFID) in the United Kingdom agreed that economic growth is a powerful instrument for poverty reduction and improved quality of life in the developing countries (DFID, 2023). However, notwithstanding the positive effect of economic growth, DFID (2023) also claimed that the national growth can have a different effect on the issue of poverty. That is, the extent of reducing poverty depends on the participation of the “poor” in the process of growth and shares in its proceeds. The sharing of proceeds of the economic growth in a fair manner is the ideal goal of inclusive economic growth (OECD, 2023). Therefore, the path to be taken by the nano business for inclusive growth is through participation in the process of economic growth as suggested by DFID. The role of the governing policies is crucial in this approach of growth inclusion. OECD (2023) cited that changing the rules to make more people able to contribute and realize the economic growth is what inclusive growth is all about.

Research Framework

The Entrepreneurship Theory of Thomas Cochran was incorporated in the research framework (see Figure 1) as it assisted the study in giving meaning to the current situations (variable A) of the nano businesses by looking at the factors (variable B) that have created impact in their journey as entrepreneurs. As a matter of fact, this theory already provided three influential factors to entrepreneurial performance: role expectations, social expectations, and personality traits. But in addition, this study also considered other influential factors that arose from the data collected for variable B. The data for variables A and B both came from the narratives gathered from the participants wherein such data were then analyzed and interpreted to be able to come up with the recommended support needed by the nano business owners.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework in exploring the lived experiences of the nano businesses in Nagcarlan, Laguna for inclusive economic growth

Philosophical Lens

The study was grounded by the interpretivism approach as a research paradigm. This worldview believes in the ontology that there are multiple realities existing through own experiences of each individual despite the occurrence of the same kind of event to those respective individuals (Pretorius, 2022). Such event refers to the nano businesses wherein research participants were all nano business owners who were the rich data sources as they have their own lived and firsthand experiences. Hence, this study also served as the voice of the nano businesses.

Research Questions

The Philippine government had already made initiative to support the informal sector through the Republic Act No. 9178 which is also known as the Barangay Micro Business Enterprises (BMBEs) Act of 2002. In this Act, those businesses belonging in the informal sector, from which the nano businesses are included, will be given an opportunity to receive grants, which is the same with the mainstream economy but subject to some certain requirements. But despite this initiative, the call for the nano businesses to be supported and recognized remains. Thus, this study provided clear perspectives about the nano businesses by answering the following research questions:

1. What are the existing conditions of the nano businesses in Nagcarlan, Laguna in terms of the following factors?
 - a. Capitalization
 - b. Expansion
 - c. Regulatory Requirements
2. What are the emerging narratives that trigger the survival of the nano businesses in the municipality of Nagcarlan?
3. What assistance can be designed to support the nano businesses in Nagcarlan, Laguna for inclusive economic growth?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the hermeneutic phenomenology which is the study of experiences that is more focused on the personalized interpretation of experiences of those individuals involved in a particular event under study. With this, the phenomenon under study was the nano business and the individuals involved who provided information about their lived experiences were the nano business owners themselves. It is believed that, in this approach, every actors involved within a phenomenon have different point of views based on how they individually interact with that same phenomenon.

Research Locale

The municipality of Nagcarlan is geographically situated near the foothill of Mt. San Cristobal and Mt. Banahaw and considered as the biggest upland town in the province of Laguna. Despite being landlocked, it has many rivers and waterfalls which attract many tourists most especially during summer season. It also has a cool weather condition with rich land area suitable for agricultural products like vegetables and fruit-bearing trees, particularly, *lanzones* and coconut. Among other economic sources of the town are their sweet delicacies and native snacks such as *uraro* cookies, *macapuno* candies, *shingaling*, and chips. In fact, these specialty products of Nagcarlan can already be seen being sold in nearby towns and cities as well as in some *pasalubong* shops in Metro Manila. Thus, being a municipality that is rich in agricultural products, with several food

manufacturers, as well as known tourist attractions, the presence of nano businesses is highly likely in the area.

Selection of Participants

The study utilized one of the purposive sampling techniques for phenomenological studies—the heterogeneous sampling—which is also known as the maximum variation sampling. This selection process considers wide range of prospective participants to ensure variations of perspectives by choosing representatives among the typical and average members of the group under study (Laerd Dissertation, 2023). Thus, this selection method follows the ontology of interpretivism worldview, which considers that each individuals have unique perspectives based on how they individually experienced the same phenomenon. Hence, there were a total of six research participants representing the food cart vendors, fruit sellers, vegetable sellers, watch mechanic, and shoe and umbrella repairers. Moreover, the principle of data saturation was also considered in the sampling design which means that the diversity and depth of information could still be acquired regardless of how small the sample size is.

Scope and Limitations

Business activities of the participants are limited to trade and services. The nano business is owned and managed by a solopreneur which means that the business is being operated without any help of a business partner or hired employees. For this study, the participants are the nano business owners who are not an employee, hired or contractual-based, of any company or institution, nor a freelancer wherein the nano business is just a part-time work for additional earnings. In other words, the research participants are the nano business owners who are usually the breadwinners in the family that run their nano businesses for daily survival.

Research Instruments

This study used the semi-structured one-on-one personal interview method using guide questions; because this method had sought to uncover what the relayed story meant as they emerged in the interview process. So, it commenced from being unstructured with the use of open questions and progressed into having that semi-structured feel by using probing questions. Moreover, observation method was used as an additional data gathering tool wherein actual business setting, behavior, and other information as they occurred were recorded and simultaneously done during the interview with the participants.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the interview proper, the participants were informed about the purpose of the study, the specified timeframe of the interview so that business activity would not be fully disturbed, the confidentiality of answers, as well as the privacy of their personal data. The one-on-one interviews were conducted in-person at the business location of the nano

business owners using guide questions while the style of interview questioning started as unstructured to be able to extract the story in a relaxed and comfortable manner on the side of the participants. With the approval of the participants, a voice recorder was also used during the interview to avoid missing out important details and the flow of conversation would not be disrupted. Meanwhile, other information were obtained by observing the actual business setting and recorded in the journal notes.

Data Construction

The data collected from the participants were constructed and analyzed using the four-step process of hermeneutic phenomenological analysis, namely, naïve reading, structural analysis, comprehensive understanding, and the critical reflection. *Naïve Reading* is more focused on the initial understanding of concepts and meaning recognition. At this point, preliminary themes and patterns started to be identified. Then, *Structural Analysis* was done by examining details through themes and patterns. While using the thematic structural analysis, emerging and meaningful themes were sought from every part of the text, sentences, or even paragraphs. Then repetitive words and phrases were collected to examine patterns, variations, and relationships between these groups of concepts. Next is the *Comprehensive Understanding* from which holistic interpretation was formed by summarizing the themes, sub-themes, and variations constructed from the structural analysis. Understanding the meanings and interpreting them were done by looking for appropriate literatures that would help deepen and widen the horizon to properly illuminate the interview texts. The main goal of this process was to open new perspectives then relate them for future meaningful experiences. Lastly, *Critical Reflection* was the final process in the data analysis plan focused more on the evaluation of the interpretations in relation to the general objectives as well as implications of this study.

RESULTS

Table 1. Summary of direct inferences constructed based on the objectives of the study.

I. Existing Conditions of the Nano Businesses
A. Capitalization
1. They are doing the business with a family member as a helper.
2. Business started with minimal budget but working capital remains at its minimum over the years.
3. They earned income but unstable at times.
4. Capital sometimes comes from loans but they prefer using own money.
5. Goal setting is important to ensure profit.
B. Expansion
1. There is no fixed business location and only rely on the availability of space outside, surrounding, the public market.
2. They are unknowingly practicing some of the marketing schemes to do good business such as:
a. They try out different means of selling goods.
b. They offer wide of range of products and services.
c. They utilize the importance of the “word-of-mouth.”
3. They are in total control on setting-up marked-up selling prices since they were knowledgeable on the best sources of raw materials; however, there were associated product risks since usual offerings are perishable items like food and snacks.
4. Their current skills and abilities are gained through self-study and on-the-job experiences.
C. Regulatory Requirements
1. They are aware about the importance of business permits.
2. Business permits are not related with the ability to do business.
3. There is also a ticketing fee being imposed to the nano business owners by the local government unit.
II. Triggering Factors to the Survival of the Nano Businesses
1. They have been influenced by a family member.
2. They utilize their abilities and other business skills.
3. They acknowledge the importance of regular customers and clients.
4. They enjoy doing the business.
5. Their needs and demands are being met by the nano business.
6. They have positive outlook.
III. Proposed Assistance for the Nano Businesses for Inclusive Economic Growth
Formulated a proposed ordinance addressed to the municipal government of Nagcarlan for the general welfare of the nano businesses in the municipality. The assistance plan will be known as the NaNoGosyo Initiatives which is an acronym that stands for the <i>Nagcarlan’s Nano Negosyo Initiatives</i> . The proposed agenda of the NaNoGosyo Initiatives are the following:
1. Minimize the required business documents of the nano businesses by allowing to secure Barangay Clearance only instead of the Mayor’s Permit;
2. Grant ease of access to finance through partnerships with different microfinance institutions and cooperatives in Nagcarlan; and
3. Organize an annual NaNoGosyo Convention.

DISCUSSION

Explanation and interpretation of the research results were further discussed in the succeeding paragraphs based on the objectives of the study as presented in Table 1.

I. Existing Conditions of the Nano Businesses

The status of capitalization and working capital is very significant as it gives signal whether to continue or to stop the business. The initial amount of capital to start a nano business only ranges from 1,000 to 10,000 Philippine Pesos. Obviously, this budget is small enough to establish a decent business, but considering their financial capability, it is still better than to have nothing to begin with. For most businesses, there is a considerable net profit margin to say that a certain business is successful and profitable. However, for the nano businesses, they regard daily earnings as either positive or negative only. But surprisingly, business losses are not a discouraging situation for them; as long as they see opportunities to earn, they are at their business as usual the following day. This positive mindset is most likely the reason why majority of the solopreneurs were able to keep their nano businesses operating for more than 10 years. On a contrary, unstable profit made them incapable to increase the working capital resulting to a stagnant and slow growth. They avoid borrowing money from lending institutions due to the possibility that their small profits will only be part of payment for loan interest. Even though some nano businesses may also need regular helpers, they prefer a family member, instead of hiring somebody else, to avoid partaking extra expense from their small income.

Furthermore, the nano businesses in Nagcarlan also have the potential to grow since they are already doing some of the basics in business, most especially on the sales, marketing, and products and services aspects. Their business knowledge is based on actual experiences, which means that learning is dependent on how they respond to the actual situations and difficulties they are encountering. Therefore, what they really need is to enhance these abilities to attain their maximum potentials. Meanwhile, fixed business location is a less significant concern at the time of study since businesses are still small and space rental fees are not yet affordable. Lastly, it was also good to note that most of the nano business owners are aware on the need to comply in securing Business Permit. However, it was not made clear if the business permit they knew is the same as the Mayor's Permit, the barangay clearance, or the daily ticket being issued to them for using a space within the public market area. This was concluded because they are not familiar with the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) which is the primary agency responsible for sole proprietors, like the nano business owners, to have their businesses be registered through a Certificate of Registration as required to obtain Mayor's Permit.

II. Triggering Factors to the Survival of the Nano Businesses

Taking the initial step of launching a business is a courageous act for the nano entrepreneurs despite their tight initial budget and limited know-how in business operation. But to be able to make such business continues running for a long period of time is also indeed an achievement. What triggers their survival? Based on the result of this study, six triggering factors were determined to have relative contributions in the survival of the nano businesses in Nagcarlan. Interestingly, after classifying these six triggering factors in parallel to the Cochran's Theory of Entrepreneurship, it was inferred that the three Cochran factors—personality traits, social expectations, and role expectations—also emerged as influential factors to the nano businesses and one additional triggering factor, which is the Main Livelihood, was found unique to the nano business.

The succeeding discussions show the classification of the six identified triggering factors that were roughly ranked according to their influence based on the frequency of the participants who benefitted from them. In the same way, the particular connection of these factors with Cochran's Theory of Entrepreneurship was also mentioned below.

➤ First: Main Livelihood

This is not included in Cochran's Theory of Entrepreneurship

This factor emerged from almost all of the interviews with the research participants. The solopreneurs' earnings remain at the lowest level; however, they have treated their nano businesses as the main and only source of income for them to survive on a daily basis and meet the emerging needs of their families.

➤ Second and Third: Positivity and Enjoyment

Cochran's Theory of Entrepreneurship: Personality Traits

Managing a nano business is a tiring task which requires perseverance and hard work. But any difficulties become bearable due to chosen business activities were something that they personally enjoy doing, resulting into contentment for whatever the business can bring to their table. Besides, they also believe that if they give-up, they will only get nothing and so, they keep the business going. These types of attitude become significant for them to endure the risks of doing business.

➤ Fourth to Sixth: Skills and Abilities; Customer Satisfaction; and Family Influence

Cochran's Theory of Entrepreneurship: Role and Social Expectations

The remaining three factors can be treated as equally contributing factors in the case of the nano businesses. First, one of the reasons why they started the business is because their parents also did the same kind of livelihood in the past as the main source of living of the whole family. In essence, there is no negative implication for the business if the parents

have greatly influenced their creations. It is indeed more advantageous on part of the children—now business owners—if they have inspirations for doing the business. But then, aside from the family, customers and clients also play important roles in the survival of the business because, obviously, without them, there will be no business. The voice of satisfied clients are the silent marketers of a good business since their words have the capability to spread like wildfire. But it should be noted that their decisions should not be fully dependent on the satisfaction of the customers alone because it might lead into business exhaustion. Nano business owners should also remember that customers have different needs and wants, and not all of them can be met by a single store alone. The important thing is that their knowledge about their customers should only be part of their considerations and motivation to continue doing what they can do best since they cannot please every customer every time. Relatively, most nano business owners did not take any study about business or entrepreneurship due to some financial and time limitations. In fact, their actions and decisions are mostly based on their prior knowledge about the business from family members and basic instincts in response to their current business needs. They are using practical abilities that have become innate in them because of the emerging needs for them to do so.

III. Proposed Assistance for the Nano Businesses for Inclusive Economic Growth

The purpose of the NaNoGosyo Initiatives is the inclusion of the nano businesses in Nagcarlan to become participants in the process of the economic growth, so that they will also receive and experience equal shares from the benefits of such growth. For them to become participants, there are rules that needed to be changed, enhanced, or added as mentioned by OECD (2023) because government policies are the only one capable in making non-participants to become qualified contributors. Therefore, the NaNoGosyo Initiatives is a proposal that is addressed to the local government unit of Nagcarlan, specifically to the municipal council—commonly known as the *Sangguniang Bayan*—which is the legislative body of the municipal government. Wherein, upon consideration and approval, the NaNoGosyo Initiatives will be implemented through a Municipal Ordinance which must contain the Implementing Rules and Regulations of the NaNoGosyo Initiatives.

The main objective of the NaNoGosyo Initiatives is to promote the welfare of the nano business to be the source of livelihood that is capable to provide a quality standard of living. This is the reason why it was formulated with three initial agenda. First is the acceptance of the Barangay Clearance as a legal substitute to the Mayor's Permit to serve as business license to operate. Since one of the requirements in securing Mayor's Permit is to have a registered business name with DTI, it is unlikely for the nano businesses to be able to secure such certification because most of them are peddlers—selling goods using strollers—and sidewalk

vendors with no permanent business addresses. The need for nano businesses to have business license is critical because this will give them easy access to affordable financial services that can help them grow the business and likewise meet the needs of their families since they will eventually be recognized as entrepreneurs. Second, when it comes to ease of access, the proposal is for the municipality to have partnership with existing microcredit and microfinance institutions operating in Nagcarlan, Laguna because they already have their own tried and tested systems, procedures, and technology in place to cover the risks of offering financial services to low-income individuals. The agreement must also ensure that nano business owners will not be exploited by providing them with affordable interest on loans, which will discourage them to approach loan sharks in the community.

Lastly, setting-up a NaNoGosyo Convention will serve as an avenue to gather all nano businesses in the municipality of Nagcarlan for empowerment and capacity enhancement. This event will be used to provide information and guidance needed by the nano businesses to further the growth of their businesses. The capacity building activities of the NaNoGosyo Convention will include, but not limited to, the following:

- a. Advancement - Learning sessions to develop the skills, abilities, and business instincts of the nano business owners particularly on financial literacy, sales, and marketing, among others
- b. Empowerment - Sharing of testimonials from the successful entrepreneurs of Nagcarlan, most especially whose businesses also started from micro businesses and sole proprietorships
- c. Promotion - Setting-up of booths in a designated area to exhibit the products and services of the nano businesses which will be open for public visits

Conclusions

This study illuminated the current situations of the nano business industry in Nagcarlan, Laguna by understanding the lived experiences of the solopreneurs. To begin with, it was concluded that the nano businesses are in stagnant condition. The business is not growing because profit is only enough for family subsistence, so there is inability to put extra amount for capital. Their skills, abilities, adaptability, and prior knowledge of the business from family members are the basic reasons why they were able to keep the business running. Through the list of constructed factors for their business survival, it can be highlighted that they have the potential for growth because they are responsive and adaptive—responsive to their needs and adaptive to whatever their present surroundings can offer to them. With this, what they need is an assistance that will be coming from the outside of their limited circle. Hence the formulation of the NaNoGosyo Initiatives which is a proposed municipal ordinance for the advancement of the nano businesses to improve the lives of the solopreneurs; and this is in fact the goal of the inclusive economic growth.

In the process of inclusive growth, it is expected that there is an equal opportunity for employment wherein such employment has the capacity to generate income for the family to reduce poverty and to provide access to the basic essential services. Encouraging the development of nano businesses through NaNoGosyo Initiatives can provide employment opportunities [Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 8 – decent work and economic growth]. Consequently, the nano businesses will then have opportunities to provide decent amount of income wherein their families can now buy more than the necessities for mere survival [SDG 1 – No Poverty and SDG 10 – Reduced Inequalities]. Finally, their families will then have the capability to send their children to proper schooling, have enough savings, can own or rent a nice home, or can avail of health care services due to their income from the nano business [SDG 3 – Good Health and Well-being]. If all these conditions will be achieved, it can be concluded that promoting the welfare of the nano businesses for inclusive economic growth is worth to be given with utmost attention, most especially if the future generation of entrepreneurs will soon consider managing their own nano businesses because they have realized its potential.

Recommendations

In inclusive economic growth, government policies are the significant factors in the attainment of its success. Since the focus of this study is on the lived experiences of the nano business owners with business activities relative to trade and services, it is recommended that supplemental studies about nano business will be conducted in Nagcarlan to support the aspirations of the NaNoGosyo Initiatives. But for a wider outreach and greater gain, it is recommended to have a national policy that is intended solely for the welfare of the nano businesses; for them to be formally recognized as a business entity with special considerations to documentary requirements, credit assistance, and upskilling, among others. On the other hand, the BMBE Law, which is intended for the microbusinesses, should be amended to include the nano businesses by providing them with special provision in securing Mayor's Permit since Certificate of Registration with DTI is also one of its requirements: provide them substitute documents that are easy and affordable to secure. In addition, it is highly recommended that further studies should be conducted for other locales to find out if the current conditions and major concerns of the nano businesses are almost the same nationwide. Furthermore, only the business side of the nano businesses was considered in this study, thus a case study is also recommended to see at a greater extent the daily living of solopreneurs and how they survive using the income they get from their nano businesses.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher of this study ensures that accepted principles of ethical and professional conduct had been followed. The study was conducted without any funding, biases, or conflict of interest. Informed consent was also obtained from all individual participants to ensure voluntary participation and each potential participant has the right to decline the interview if they wish to do so. Before conducting the interview, the

researcher asked permission to record the whole conversation through audio recording. In due courtesy to the business hours of the solopreneurs, the participants were also informed that the interview will only take about 20 to 30 minutes of their time. All information and data gathered from the participants were used as intended and solely for the purpose of this research. Confidentiality of responses and anonymity of the research participants were observed to avoid potential harm in accordance to the Republic Act No. 10173 which is also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012. In addition, proper citations and acknowledgment were observed in reference to the works and ideas of other authors and sources.

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